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List of Acronyms

BGO	Bismuth Germanate
CDAW	Coordinated Data Analysis Workshop
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
CsI(Tl)	(Thallium activated) Cesium Iodide
CUSUM	Cumulative Sum
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument (on-board SOHO)
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and electron Experiment (on-board SOHO)
EU	European Union
GBM	Gamma-ray Burst Monitor (of the Fermi Gamma-ray Space Telescope)
GEANT	Geometry and Tracking (Monte-Carlo simulation toolkit)
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement (of cosmic rays)
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite
HED	High Energy Detector (of ERNE)
khp	keyhole period
LASCO	Large Angle and Spectrometric Coronagraph
LED	Low Energy Detector (of ERNE)
lels	low energy loss statistics
RHESSI	Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SSD	Solid State Detector
STIX	Spectrometer Telescope for Imaging X-rays
SXR	Soft X-ray
STEREO	Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory
WAVES	Radio and Plasma Wave Investigation
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the first results from the systematic analysis work, performed on the following datasets: Solar and Heliospheric Observatory ([SOHO](#)) / Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and electron Experiment ([ERNE](#)), [SOHO](#) / Electron Proton Helium Instrument ([EPHIN](#)), Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite ([GOES](#)) X-rays, [SOHO](#) / Large Angle and Spectrometric Coronagraph ([LASCO](#)), Wind / WAVES and Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory ([STEREO](#)) / WAVES resulting in a catalog of SEP events at 1 AU, with complete coverage over solar cycles 23 and 24 while further pertaining to the ongoing solar cycle 25. This is the first catalog of the SPECification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data ([SPEARHEAD](#)) project, funded by the Horizon Europe framework programme of the European Union ([EU](#)). The catalog is based on high-energy (>100 MeV) protons from [SOHO](#) / [ERNE](#) and proton recordings of the events by [SOHO](#) / [EPHIN](#). A total of 169 energetic particle events have been identified. The current document details the methodologies applied during the identification of the Solar Energetic Particle ([SEP](#)) events, the obtained [SEP](#) characteristics and the solar associations. It further includes the catalog and details its outputs.

1 Introduction

Utilizing very high-energy particle observations from the most important heliophysics missions combined with ground based measurements, SPECification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD) will provide answers to three science questions:

1. How are protons accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions?
2. What are the release times and spectral characteristics of near-relativistic particles from solar eruptions?
3. How do coronal and interplanetary structures affect the transport processes of very high energetic particles?

To enable the scientific data analysis SPEARHEAD has three technical objectives:

1. Determining the response functions of a large number of spacecraft instruments to derive high-energy particle fluxes from observations at unprecedented accuracy releasing revised and completely new datasets
2. Performing cross-calibration of datasets measured by science-grade and monitoring instruments to enable the use of monitoring data for scientific analyses
3. Combining high-energy particle and context observations together with modeling of plasma structures for easier in-depth analysis of solar eruptions, quantifying their effect and delivering them to the community.

This document describes the first release of one of the catalogs produced by SPEARHEAD, i.e., the catalog of >100-MeV proton events. The catalog is based on multiple solar and heliospheric datasets described in §2, which also describes the methods that have been used in the production of the catalog. The actual catalog entries are described in §3, and conclusions and outlook of the work is presented in §4.

2 Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

2.1.1 SOHO / ERNE Penetrating Particle Counter

The identification of events in the catalog is done using counter data from Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and electron Experiment (ERNE) (Torsti et al. 1995) on-board Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO). ERNE consists of two multi-layer particle telescopes, Low Energy Detector (LED) and High Energy Detector (HED). The data used in this deliverable (Vainio et al. 2024, hereafter D5.1) come from HED. HED consists of a hodoscope with four layers of silicon strip detectors (thickness = 0.3 mm each), a fifth detector layer made of silicon (thickness = 1 mm, referred to as detector D1) followed by two scintillator layers made of (Thallium activated) Cesium Iodide (CsI(Tl)) (8 mm, D2) and Bismuth Germanate (BGO) (15 mm, D3), respectively. Below the stack, there is a plastic scintillator (6 mm, AC1) designed to trigger to particles penetrating the whole stack. In particular, we use the penetrating particle counter of HED, which responds primarily to protons above 100 MeV energies. The response of the channel is still being investigated in Work Package (WP) 2 using Geometry and Tracking (GEANT) simulations (Agostinelli et al. 2003) (see details in Deliverable D2.1; Köberle et al. 2024) as well as in WP3 using cross-calibration to other datasets. This is why this deliverable, D5.1 (i.e., the first release of the catalog) uses the counting rates instead of particle intensities derived from the counting rate.

Figure 1: Simulated response function of the [ERNE/HED](#) penetrating particle counter taking into account both forward and backward penetrating particles. For the latter, we have assumed that the spacecraft structures below the instrument correspond to an aluminum layer of 10 cm thickness. The different curves correspond to different (unknown) trigger levels of the bottom-most plastic scintillator in the stack.

A preliminary response function, simulated with [GEANT](#), is plotted in Fig. 1 for different (still unknown) triggering levels of the plastic scintillator at the bottom of the stack. It is evident that the effective energy of the counter is above 100 MeV, and the standard bow-tie analysis gives them in the range of 129–156 MeV (Fig. 2) for the threshold level between 0.5 and 5 MeV.

To make it easier to recognize Solar Energetic Particle ([SEP](#)) events from other variations in the data (see subsection 2.2.1), we also make use of a counter of particles stopping in the D3 detector (just above the AC1), sensitive to protons at about 50–100 MeV. An example of one month of time series of D3 and AC1 counters is provided in Fig. 3.

Especially during the first years of the [SOHO](#) mission, there are some longer data gaps in [ERNE](#) observations due to various instrument and spacecraft anomalies. For 1996–2017 these gaps are listed by [Paassilta et al. \(2017\)](#). The ones lasting seven days or longer¹ are:

- 24 June 1998 – 9 October 1998
- 21 December 1998 – 8 February 1999
- 13 – 31 March 2000
- 10 – 17 August 2001
- 5 – 12 February 2002
- 28 February – 11 March 2003
- 22 – 29 April 2004
- 6 – 12 August 2004
- 26 November – 11 December 2006
- 9 July – 14 August 2009
- 7 – 24 September 2009
- 30 November 2011 – 5 January 2012

¹Some of the gaps given by [Paassilta et al. \(2017\)](#) may contain short periods of data but are still listed as data gaps for practical reasons, i.e., because meaningful event detection inside the gaps would not be possible.

Figure 2: Geometric factor (top) and effective energy (bottom), obtained using bow-tie analysis, of the penetrating particle counter as a function of plastic scintillator detection threshold ("AC Threshold").

Figure 3: Example of ERNE counter observations [in counts per 5 minutes] from November 1997, where two consecutive >100 MeV proton events are detected, starting on 4 and 6 November, respectively. The counter labeled AC1 is the penetrating particle counter and the one labeled D3 corresponds to particles stopping in the bottom of the detector stack, i.e., not triggering the plastic scintillator.

- 28 January – 10 February 2012
- 9 December 2012 – 31 January 2013
- 29 October – 4 December 2013.

After 2013, the longest consecutive data gap is about 4 days long. Since 2004, the data also experience frequent shorter data gaps, related to the reduced telemetry rate of the [SOHO](#) spacecraft during the so-called keyhole period ([khp](#)) (see also subsection [2.2.2](#)), when the pointing of the high-gain antenna is not optimal for communications. During those times, the accuracy of the event timing is sometimes compromised. For the first release of the catalog, we have not attempted to fill these gaps with other data.

All [SOHO](#) / [ERNE](#) data gaps longer than 24 h are listed in the [Appendix](#).

2.1.2 [SOHO](#) / [EPHIN](#) High-energy protons data

Electron Proton Helium Instrument ([EPHIN](#)) measures particles – protons, electrons and helium – across a wide range of energies from MeV to several hundred of MeV (for details see [Müller-Mellin et al. 1995](#)). As discussed in [Kühl et al. \(2015, 2016, 2017\)](#) the $\frac{dE}{dx} - \frac{dE}{dx}$ -method can be applied to the integral channel of [EPHIN](#) to achieve proton energy spectra from 50 MeV to above 1 GeV. The method to extend the energy range of [EPHIN](#) for protons up to energies of above 1 GeV based on the energy loss data from Solid State Detectors ([SSDs](#)) A to D, is discussed in detail in [Heber et al. \(2024\)](#) (hereafter D3.1). Utilizing extensive [GEANT4](#) simulations ([Agostinelli et al. 2003](#)) of the instrument (see also [Köberle et al. 2024](#), hereafter D2.1), it has been shown that the initial energy of a given proton penetrating [EPHIN](#) (i.e., triggering detectors A to F) can be derived from the energy losses in [SSD C](#) and [D](#). However, a separation of forward and backward penetrating protons is not possible, so the contribution of backward penetrating particles must be calculated (see also D2.1). Due to aging of one thick [SSD](#) of the instrument, the method needed to be adapted to a thin [SSD](#), here [SSD B](#). With [SSD D](#) becoming noisy in 2017, the method of [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#) could not be applied directly.

As explained by [Kühl et al. \(2016\)](#), the energy resolution of the method relies on the energy loss resolution in the [SSDs](#) involved. Thus, utilizing in total 3300 μm instead of 8000 μm silicon we expect a severe reduction of the energy resolution.

Figure 4 shows on the left and right panels the energy loss per mm distribution of the [SSDs](#) B (black), C (red) and D (green) during 11 May 2024 ([GLE74](#); [Rouillard et al. 2024](#), hereafter D4.2). The distribution in [SSD D](#) is very different from the other ones. As a consequence, energy losses per mm $\frac{dE}{dx} < 1.5$ MeV/mm are strongly influenced by the noise in [SSD D](#). The right panel displays the minimum energy loss per mm utilizing [SSDs C](#) and [D](#) (black) and [SSDs C](#) and [B](#) (red), respectively. Note that significant differences are found for energy losses per millimeter below $\frac{dE}{dx} \leq 0.5$ MeV/mm. The workaround has been described in detail in [Heber et al. \(2024\)](#) and results in proton energy spectra in the energy range from 50 MeV to above 600 MeV. Figure 5 compares the result of the method for two events reported by [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#).

In D3.1 we conclude that the measurements are in good agreement within the energy range from 50 to 200 MeV and differ by less than 30% below 600 MeV, which is in the range of the uncertainty estimated by [Kühl et al. \(2017\)](#). Another finding is the reduced energy resolution as can be seen when comparing with the spectra presented in [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#).

In order to derive a proxy for >100 MeV proton fluxes from [EPHIN](#), [GEANT](#) simulations with electrons, protons and helium were performed. The goal of the study is to determine the energy range for which the smallest contribution of electrons and helium is found.

For this purpose we computed a count rate

$$C\left(\frac{dE}{dx}; t\right) = \sum_{\alpha=e,p,\text{He}} \int_{E=0}^{\infty} F_{\Delta E}(E, \alpha) J_{\alpha}(E, t) dE, \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: $\frac{dE}{dx}$ distribution of SSDs B (black histogram), C (red histogram) and D (green histogram) on May 11, 2024 (GLE74). While the $\frac{dE}{dx}$ distributions for SSD B agrees well with the one of SSD C the distribution in SSD D differs significantly from the others below 1.5 MeV/mm. The influence on the minima of the energy loss in SSD B and C differs from the one obtained utilizing SSD D and C for energy losses below 0.5 MeV/mm.

where $F_{\Delta E}(E, \alpha)$ is EPHIN's energy response function (for an energy loss rate $\frac{dE}{dx}$ computed from the energy losses ΔE in its B and C detectors) and $J_{\alpha}(E, t)$ are the a-priori unknown energy spectra for each particle type of interest. $C(\frac{dE}{dx}; t)$ is here determined using power-law spectra with spectral index $\gamma = -1$ and a helium to proton ratio of 0.1. The scaling of electrons to protons is arbitrary chosen because of the very different energy ranges and electron to proton ratios during SEP-events (see for example Dresing et al. 2024, and references therein). Fig. 6 shows the results for electrons (green), protons (blue) and helium (orange) separately. At $\frac{dE}{dx}$ above 1.13 MeV/mm (see the second vertical solid black line at Fig. 6) the corresponding distribution of below 100 MeV protons and above a few hundred MeV/amu helium become ambiguous until the energy loss per mm exceeds about 2.5 MeV/mm when helium becomes the dominant element. At low $\frac{dE}{dx}$, protons and electrons compete with each other. Below $\frac{dE}{dx} = 0.56$ MeV/mm measurements (see the first vertical solid black line at Fig. 6) can be dominated by above 6 MeV electrons during SEP periods and above $\frac{dE}{dx} = 1.13$ MeV/mm by relativistic helium during quiet time periods (Kühl et al. 2015, 2016, and references therein). The two vertical lines that have been added to the figure indicate the selected energy loss per path-length range. **Therefore, in what follows the flux of above 100 MeV protons is approximated by an energy channel for which $\frac{dE}{dx}$ ranges from $\frac{dE}{dx} = 0.56$ MeV/mm to $\frac{dE}{dx} = 1.13$ MeV/mm.**

The left panel of Fig. 7 displays the energy response function of the >100-MeV proxy. The channel is mainly sensitive to protons with energies from about 120 MeV up to 450 MeV. The Bow-tie method (see Gieseler et al. 2024, hereafter D6.1) has been applied to determine the effective energy E_{eff} and the Response factor R . Utilizing power laws with spectral index γ between $\gamma = -2$ and $\gamma = -5$ we find $E_{\text{eff}} = 189$ MeV and $R = 60.34$ cm² sr MeV, respectively.

As an example Fig. 8 displays in the left and right panel the time profile of the above 100 MeV proxy flux from the EPHIN proxy during GLE73 (28 October 2021) and the time of maximum proton spectrum, respectively. For the time profiles, an averaging period of 10 minutes is used. In the following section, the methodology on how the onset time, the background flux, peak flux, and fluence are determined, is presented.

Figure 5: Proton energy flux spectra from [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#) (red symbols) and from deliverable D3.1 (black symbols) and the corresponding differences are shown in the left and right panels, respectively. The upper and lower panel give the results utilizing 10 energy bins for the [GLE72](#) and for the January 6, 2014 sub-[GLE](#) event, respectively (for details see deliverable D3.1).

Figure 6: Contribution of electrons (green histogram), protons (blue histogram) and helium (orange histogram) as function of the minimum energy loss per path-length in solid-state detector B and C allowing to minimize the contribution of helium and electrons to a >100 MeV integral proton channel (for details see text).

Figure 7: Left panel: Computed response function of an above 100 MeV EPHIN proxy. In order to determine the effective energy E_{eff} the bow-tie method (see deliverable D6.1) has been applied utilizing power laws with index between $\gamma = 2$ and $\gamma = 5$. Here only the central response is taken into account in order to minimize instrumental effects that occur at high flux level.

Figure 8: Left panel: Time profile of the above 100 MeV proxy flux from the EPHIN proxy during GLE73 (October 28, 2021). An averaging period of 10 minutes are used here. The right panel displays the energy spectra obtained between 19:40h and 21:40h during the event maximum.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Event detection and onset-time determination

The cataloged events are detected using the AC1 channel of ERNE. We run the Poisson – Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) method (e.g., Huttunen-Heikinmaa et al. 2005; Palmroos et al. 2022) over the whole time series from May 1996 to August 2024 and record the instances when the method indicates that the process is out of control. This provides a preliminary identification of events. An SEP event has typically an energy spectrum decreasing as a function of energy strong enough so that the D3 counter has a higher rate than the AC1 counter. Thus, on top of the identifications in the counting rate of AC1, we further check that each detected event in AC1 is accompanied by an event in D3 counter with higher peak rate than that in AC1.

The event detection algorithm cycles a 24-hour detection window through the data set in 3-hour increments. The first six hours of the detection window are reserved for the pre-event background, and the remaining 18 hours of the detection window are then inspected for an event, i.e., elevated proton count levels. If no event is found in the detection window, it is shifted forward by three hours. However, if an event is found, the detection window is shifted forward by nine hours to avoid detecting the same event multiple times. Figure 9 shows as an example one of the events from the catalog (Event No 133 on 2017-09-06 12:25 UT), where the six-hour rolling background is displayed with a semi-transparent red overlay, and the two relevant Poisson-CUSUM parameters, μ and $\mu_d = \mu + n \cdot \sigma$ ($n = 5$) are shown as the dashed and dotted horizontal lines, respectively. μ_d is not, however, the detection threshold itself, but rather defines the k parameter that restricts the growth of the CUSUM function (see Palmroos et al. 2022, for details).

The algorithm may detect false positives, often caused by depressed proton counts returning to normal baseline levels (e.g., Forbush decreases; Papaioannou et al. 2020; Dumbović et al. 2024), or detect duplicate events separated by a few to one time bins. Such cases were checked and verified manually.

2.2.2 SEP peak flux and fluence determined by (SOHO / EPHIN)

From EPHIN we obtain the background and peak flux of the event in question. As explained above the method relies on the number of available energy loss data from EPHIN. Due to the limited transmission rate the number for the integral channel before 2022 can be low. The left panel of Fig. 10 shows as an

Figure 9: A detection of an event in the AC 1 channel on 2017-09-06 12:25. The pre-event background is highlighted with red on the left side, of the figure. The two red horizontal lines mark the background mean (dashed) and the background mean + $n \times$ background standard deviation (dotted), where $n = 5$ is a parameter that controls the detection threshold. The solid vertical red line marks the detected onset time of the event.

example the event on 1 October 2001. The vertical line gives the onset time determined by SOHO / ERNE. The black and red curves show the hourly averaged flux and count rate of the >100-MeV proton proxy and the single detector count rate of the SSD F. The latter is a proxy for >50-MeV protons, >50-MeV/amu helium and >6-MeV electrons. The data gaps seen in the >100-MeV proton proxy are caused by the fact that the whole energy loss buffer is taken by lower energy particles. The priority scheme has been changed in 2022, leading to an improved statistics since then. In the catalog the corresponding events are indicated by low energy loss statistics (lels).

Another impact on the data coverage are due to SOHO keyhole periods: SOHO keyhole periods are specific times when the SOHO spacecraft experiences interruptions or limitations in its operations due to the alignment of the antenna to Earth. These periods typically last a few days to a couple of weeks. During keyhole periods, data transmission is reduced or even corrupted. They occur at predictable intervals,

Figure 10: Examples of “low energy loss statistics” (lels; panel on the left hand side) and “keyhole period” (khp; panel on the right hand side). See text for details.

Figure 11: Example of the fluence calculation from SOHO / EPHIN. The magenta lines depict the start and end time, as well as the background used for the integration.

generally once or twice a year, depending on the spacecraft’s orbital dynamics and the relative positions of Earth, SOHO, and the Sun. The impact of such a keyhole period was observed, for example, during the 20 September 2024 SEP event (see the right panel in Fig. 10). Here both data gaps occur during the same time. These periods are marked by *khp* in the catalog.

To rely on a reasonable counting statistics the temporal resolution of the >100-MeV proton flux proxy is taken to be 1 hour. As background period, we choose the same as ERNE (see details of the catalog below – Column I). The onset time of the event is also taken from the ERNE measurements (Column C to H). The peak flux is given by the maximum of the >100-MeV proxy reached within a few hours. The fluence is computed from the onset time to the time, when the flux either reaches 50 to 10% of the peak flux or is below 3σ to 5σ of the background flux. Fig. 11 depicts the Ground Level Enhancement (GLE) 73 as recorded at the >100 MeV EPHIN proxy (similar to the left panel of Fig. 8) indicating with vertical purple lines the start and end time, as well as, with a horizontal purple line, the chosen background of the integration for the calculation of the fluence. The obtained values are reported in the catalog (Column M).

2.3 Solar Associations

Solar associations of the identified SEP events were based on: (a) already published catalogs (like the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) >10 MeV proton catalog²), (b) inspection of all available data sources for soft X-ray flares³ and Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs), i.e., SOHO / Large Angle and Spectrometric Coronagraph (LASCO) (Brueckner et al. 1995) catalog available at Coordinated Data Analysis Workshop (CDAW) Data Center⁴; (c) inspection of radio signatures from Wind / Radio and Plasma Wave Investigation (WAVES) (Bougeret et al. 1995) and Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) / WAVES (Bougeret et al. 2008), complemented by ground based observations^{5,6} where possible, as well as a search for possible signatures in hard X-rays from Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager (RHESSI) (Lin et al. 2003) and Spectrometer Telescope for Imaging X-rays (STIX) (Krucker et al. 2020). Gamma-ray counterparts were also inspected from Fermi / Gamma-ray Burst Monitor (GBM) (Meegan et al. 2009) for events that occurred from 2011 onwards.

A first scan of the ERNE data resulted to 173 candidate enhancements that would potentially be SEP events. Out of these, 4/(173) were deleted from the catalog after being identified as “false positive”

²https://cdaw.gsfc.nasa.gov/CME_list/sepe/

³<https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/stp/satellite/goes-r.html>

⁴https://cdaw.gsfc.nasa.gov/CME_list/

⁵<https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/stp/space-weather/solar-data/solar-features/solar-radio/radio-bursts/reports/spectral-listings/>

⁶<https://www.solarmonitor.org/data/>

identifications, mainly due to a slight rebound during the declining phase of a previous event. As a result, a total of 169 **SEP** events were identified in the **SPEARHEAD** >100 MeV proton catalog. For the majority (87%; 147/169) of these events a reliable solar association in terms of flares and **CMEs** was determined. For 22 events, several solar associations were possible, a choice was made (see, e.g., Deliverable D4.2; [Rouillard et al. 2024](#)) and the other potential solar associations were included in the notes of the catalog. Our solar associations were further cross-checked against catalogs published by [Cane et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Paassilta et al. \(2017\)](#) and for those events that were common, the associations appeared to match. 19 events had a wrongly estimated onset, due to the presence of data gaps in **ERNE** data or a very slow rising phase. For each of them, we carefully looked at the particle flux to estimate a more realistic onset and search for a solar association with the precedent described method. **Details on the solar associations are provided in the D4.2.**

3 First Release of the Catalog

The First Release of the >100 MeV proton event catalog is based on the scanning of **SOHO** / **ERNE** / **HED** measurements – for the first time available for particles penetrating the instrument at an energy above 100 MeV – complemented with **SEP** characteristics from **SOHO** / **EPHIN** and with comprehensive solar associations. Therefore, the first **SPEARHEAD** catalog provides a broad overview of very high energy **SEP** events, directly addressing the first Science Question put forth by the project.

The catalog includes 169 **SEP** events and is currently available at <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/s/dZ8przjLQNjF4xf>. The catalog will be provided through a public repository (i.e., Zenodo) at a later stage, providing the **SPEARHEAD** consortium with time to further explore the science that will be extracted by the catalog in due time within the project.

Columns A-B provide the numbering of the event and its identifier, columns C-I provide the date of the **SEP** event occurrence (including the year, month, day, hour, minute and second denoting the start time of the **SEP** event at >100 MeV, as well as the background mean of the channel used in the analysis), columns J-M present the onset time and background used as well as the obtained **SEP** characteristics (peak flux and fluence) from **SOHO** / **EPHIN** at >100 MeV. Columns N–T display the relevant solar flare information in terms of flare start time (date and time), flare peak time (date and time), magnitude (Soft X-ray (**SXR**) peak flux), position (longitude, latitude), and spacecraft observer. Column U provides the hard X-ray information where available. Columns V to AB provide identifications of type III radio bursts at ground based and spacecraft detectors including the station and timing (start dates and times), columns AC to AK mark the occurrence (or not) of a type II radio burst following the same pattern as before (i.e., station, timing information) while further including the frequency range. Column AL provides the γ -ray identifications, where possible. Columns AM-AP show the **CME** information, in terms of date of the **CME**, the plane-of-sky **CME** speed and the **CME** width, further identifying the source of the **CME** identification (i.e., **SOHO** / **LASCO**). Column AQ provides the corresponding **GLE** reference number⁷. Column AR gives the shock-reconstruction information where available and Column AS provides comments relevant to each of the **SEP** events (if any), outputted by the analysis while also include references to other published **SEP** catalogs, which is the output of the cross-evaluation of all other available **SEP** lists.

In detail, the catalog is structured as follows:

- Columns A and B: identification of the event
 - Column A: Number in the catalog
 - Column B: Identifier
- Columns C to I: **SOHO** / **ERNE** data information
 - Columns C to H: Date and time of onset (in UT)

⁷<https://gle.oulu.fi/>

- Column I: Background mean of the channel (counts)
- Columns J to M: **SOHO** / **EPHIN** data information
 - Column J: Background of the of >100 MeV proton proxy channel [$1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr s MeV})$]
 - Column K: Peak flux of the event [$1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr s MeV})$]
 - Column L: Fluence of the event [$1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr MeV})$]
 - Column M: End time (for the integration) (in DOY)
- Columns N to T: X-rays flare information
 - Columns N and O: Date and time of onset (in UT)
 - Columns P and Q: Date and time of peak flux (in UT)
 - Column R: soft X-ray class (1–8 Å soft X-ray peak intensity in terms of C, M and X nomenclature where these represent intensities of 10^{-6} , 10^{-5} , and 10^{-4} W/m^2 respectively)
 - Column S: X-ray location on the solar surface (in Stonyhurst heliographic coordinates, degrees North (N) or South (S), and East (E) or West (W))
 - Column T: Spacecraft observer
- Column U: hard X-ray flare instrument of observation (if any)
- Columns V to AB: Radio type III information
 - Column V: Ground-based station
 - Columns W and X: Start date and time of radio type III measured on ground (in UT)
 - Column Y: Spacecraft/Instrument
 - Columns ZZ and AA: Start date and time of radio type III measured on board (in UT)
 - Column AB: Notes on radio type III
- Columns AC to AK: Radio type II information
 - Columns AC to AD: Ground-based information
 - * Column AC: Station
 - * Columns AD and AE: Start date and time of radio type II measured on ground (in UT)
 - * Column AF: Frequency range [MHz]
 - Columns AG to AJ: On board information
 - * Column AG: Spacecraft/Instrument
 - * Columns AH and AI: Start date and time of radio type II measured on board (in UT)
 - * Column AJ: Frequency range [kHz]
 - Column AK: Notes on radio type II
- Columns AL: Gamma-rays information
- Columns AM to AP: **CME** information
 - Column AM: Start date of the **CME** (in UT)
 - Column AN: Linear speed of the **CME** [km/s]
 - Column AO: Angular width of the **CME** [deg]
 - Column AP: Source of information
- Column AQ: **GLE** number (if any)
- Column AR: Shock reconstruction information
- Column AS: Notes

4 Conclusions and Outlook

In this document, a list of **SEP** events at a proton energy >100 MeV has been compiled and presented. This list demonstrates results from the first year of **SPEARHEAD**: the first **SEP** event catalog. This was

based on a systematic scan of proton data at >100 MeV observed by [SOHO / ERNE](#) over the years 1997–2024. A total of 169 proton events were identified and analyzed using data from [SOHO / ERNE](#) and [SOHO / EPHIN](#), while further solar associations were identified. This first release of the catalog constitutes **Deliverable D5.1** of the project. Further releases will include more events observed in the active phase of solar cycle 25 as well as revised data on the present events, where needed.

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Appendix: Data gaps of SOHO / ERNE

The following list contains all data gaps longer than 24 hours in the SOHO / ERNE dataset until the end of November 2024.

start time	end time	duration
1996-05-28 08:26:43+00	1996-05-31 16:42:57+00	3 days 08:16:14
1996-06-02 23:59:21+00	1996-06-04 00:00:13+00	1 day 00:00:52
1997-02-15 10:22:30+00	1997-02-16 16:47:35+00	1 day 06:25:05
1997-02-25 14:43:33+00	1997-03-04 16:02:36+00	7 days 01:19:03
1997-10-25 05:26:30+00	1997-10-28 17:27:33+00	3 days 12:01:03
1997-11-19 05:06:22+00	1997-11-21 22:38:17+00	2 days 17:31:55
1997-11-26 23:59:36+00	1997-11-28 00:00:28+00	1 day 00:00:52
1998-02-25 04:50:02+00	1998-02-28 15:02:11+00	3 days 10:12:09
1998-06-24 23:12:50+00	1998-10-09 11:17:06+00	106 days 12:04:16
1998-11-14 16:05:20+00	1998-11-21 16:04:27+00	6 days 23:59:07
1998-12-01 13:04:20+00	1998-12-03 14:16:02+00	2 days 01:11:42
1998-12-21 17:26:37+00	1999-02-08 21:18:50+00	49 days 03:52:13
1999-02-14 13:49:26+00	1999-02-18 13:52:55+00	4 days 00:03:29
1999-05-21 12:52:23+00	1999-05-26 16:06:36+00	5 days 03:14:13
1999-06-03 15:06:39+00	1999-06-04 15:40:30+00	1 day 00:33:51
1999-08-19 13:06:03+00	1999-08-20 18:47:39+00	1 day 05:41:36
1999-11-15 13:55:56+00	1999-11-20 16:17:11+00	5 days 02:21:15
1999-11-28 11:51:23+00	1999-11-29 22:38:45+00	1 day 10:47:22
1999-12-01 18:37:42+00	1999-12-02 23:57:19+00	1 day 05:19:37
2000-01-07 00:24:53+00	2000-01-08 01:03:44+00	1 day 00:38:51
2000-02-22 17:11:19+00	2000-02-23 18:26:08+00	1 day 01:14:49
2000-03-13 18:05:45+00	2000-03-14 19:27:34+00	1 day 01:21:49
2000-03-29 13:26:57+00	2000-03-31 20:21:23+00	2 days 06:54:26
2000-04-18 13:20:27+00	2000-04-19 15:05:14+00	1 day 01:44:47
2000-05-22 02:49:39+00	2000-05-24 14:49:50+00	2 days 12:00:11
2001-01-14 20:58:58+00	2001-01-15 21:12:50+00	1 day 00:13:52
2001-07-02 14:31:00+00	2001-07-03 16:00:48+00	1 day 01:29:48
2001-08-10 15:34:02+00	2001-08-17 16:49:06+00	7 days 01:15:04
2002-01-01 22:45:34+00	2002-01-03 19:26:29+00	1 day 20:40:55
2002-01-24 16:16:59+00	2002-01-25 16:47:50+00	1 day 00:30:51
2002-02-05 02:36:07+00	2002-02-12 15:40:47+00	7 days 13:04:40
2002-05-23 23:59:48+00	2002-05-25 00:00:41+00	1 day 00:00:53
2003-02-28 17:53:43+00	2003-03-11 15:02:28+00	10 days 21:08:45
2004-01-19 07:03:10+00	2004-01-22 14:07:28+00	3 days 07:04:18

2004-03-25 23:59:04+00	2004-03-27 00:03:56+00	1 day 00:04:52
2004-04-01 23:59:11+00	2004-04-03 00:00:03+00	1 day 00:00:52
2004-04-22 21:41:39+00	2004-04-29 12:49:11+00	6 days 15:07:32
2004-08-06 09:16:53+00	2004-08-12 12:31:59+00	6 days 03:15:06
2005-07-31 03:37:57+00	2005-08-03 12:37:10+00	3 days 08:59:13
2006-08-13 03:23:22+00	2006-08-14 12:46:48+00	1 day 09:23:26
2007-01-27 09:39:03+00	2007-01-29 14:41:04+00	2 days 05:02:01
2010-09-26 14:57:51+00	2010-09-27 17:38:36+00	1 day 02:40:45
2010-12-10 14:39:25+00	2010-12-15 15:26:45+00	5 days 00:47:20
2011-01-09 07:49:58+00	2011-01-13 12:28:15+00	4 days 04:38:17
2011-04-06 23:59:15+00	2011-04-08 00:00:08+00	1 day 00:00:53
2011-11-30 14:43:44+00	2011-12-07 15:26:49+00	7 days 00:43:05
2011-12-07 15:42:48+00	2012-01-05 10:50:23+00	28 days 19:07:35
2012-01-22 19:42:50+00	2012-01-24 20:15:33+00	2 days 00:32:43
2012-01-25 09:09:57+00	2012-01-27 16:14:22+00	2 days 07:04:25
2012-01-28 14:08:20+00	2012-01-30 19:46:49+00	2 days 05:38:29
2012-01-30 19:55:49+00	2012-02-10 17:03:34+00	10 days 21:07:45
2012-02-15 10:43:14+00	2012-02-16 18:47:43+00	1 day 08:04:29
2012-05-11 23:26:28+00	2012-05-14 19:36:16+00	2 days 20:09:48
2012-05-21 23:59:10+00	2012-05-23 00:00:03+00	1 day 00:00:53
2012-07-06 23:35:38+00	2012-07-09 00:00:22+00	2 days 00:24:44
2012-11-02 00:51:43+00	2012-11-07 20:44:10+00	5 days 19:52:27
2012-12-06 13:01:52+00	2012-12-07 15:44:37+00	1 day 02:42:45
2012-12-09 04:29:54+00	2012-12-11 19:09:57+00	2 days 14:40:03
2012-12-11 19:24:57+00	2013-01-31 20:59:27+00	51 days 01:34:30
2013-02-01 16:46:31+00	2013-02-05 15:01:06+00	3 days 22:14:35
2013-05-06 12:28:53+00	2013-05-07 19:15:27+00	1 day 06:46:34
2013-05-10 12:40:23+00	2013-05-13 12:48:00+00	3 days 00:07:37
2013-06-08 11:24:47+00	2013-06-10 12:36:29+00	2 days 01:11:42
2013-07-17 15:22:41+00	2013-07-22 13:40:09+00	4 days 22:17:28
2013-09-07 15:51:07+00	2013-09-09 13:14:00+00	1 day 21:22:53
2013-09-29 11:51:33+00	2013-09-30 16:45:11+00	1 day 04:53:38
2013-10-29 10:47:49+00	2013-10-30 12:35:36+00	1 day 01:47:47
2013-10-30 12:36:36+00	2013-12-04 15:35:04+00	35 days 02:58:28
2014-01-29 15:55:00+00	2014-01-31 15:03:47+00	1 day 23:08:47
2014-03-20 23:59:19+00	2014-03-22 00:00:12+00	1 day 00:00:53
2014-09-20 23:59:10+00	2014-09-22 00:00:02+00	1 day 00:00:52
2014-12-17 10:57:42+00	2014-12-19 20:35:59+00	2 days 09:38:17
2015-01-09 08:08:56+00	2015-01-15 18:34:26+00	6 days 10:25:30
2015-01-24 04:24:58+00	2015-01-26 14:45:14+00	2 days 10:20:16
2015-03-23 07:48:31+00	2015-03-24 15:35:01+00	1 day 07:46:30
2015-11-06 17:57:19+00	2015-11-09 21:42:46+00	3 days 03:45:27
2015-11-14 12:47:33+00	2015-11-16 12:42:18+00	1 day 23:54:45
2015-12-02 10:07:25+00	2015-12-03 10:18:17+00	1 day 00:10:52
2015-12-10 00:26:51+00	2015-12-11 14:05:06+00	1 day 13:38:15
2016-01-05 11:47:03+00	2016-01-08 19:08:20+00	3 days 07:21:17
2016-07-21 22:43:20+00	2016-07-25 13:02:17+00	3 days 14:18:57

2016-12-21 01:26:04+00	2016-12-22 15:24:18+00	1 day 13:58:14
2017-01-08 10:23:22+00	2017-01-09 15:05:01+00	1 day 04:41:39
2017-09-10 03:47:51+00	2017-09-11 10:33:24+00	1 day 06:45:33
2018-10-12 19:10:09+00	2018-10-16 22:17:30+00	4 days 03:07:21
2019-08-06 02:12:26+00	2019-08-07 19:25:30+00	1 day 17:13:04
2020-12-04 14:59:40+00	2020-12-05 19:04:21+00	1 day 04:04:41
2021-03-12 12:35:26+00	2021-03-14 14:00:07+00	2 days 01:24:41
2022-08-22 23:59:27+00	2022-08-24 00:00:19+00	1 day 00:00:52